

Terpenoids-Part LXII: New Synthesis of 2, 6-Dimethyl-3, 6-epoxyoct-7-enol (\pm)-Lilac Alcohol

O. P. VIG, R. S. BHATT, JATINDER KAUR AND J. C. KAPUR

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14

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Synthesis of a diastereoisomeric mixture (\pm) lilac alcohol(I) has been accomplished through the cyclisation of 2,6-dimethyl-oct-2,7-diene-7-oleate with sodium hydride in benzene followed by reduction with lithium aluminium hydride.

LILAC alcohol, a monoterpene, has recently been isolated from lilac flower oil from *Syringa vulgaris* L.¹ On the basis of spectroscopic studies and its hydrogenation to 2,6-dimethyl-3,6-epoxy octanol (II), constitution I has been assigned to it¹, corroborated by a synthesis².

In view of the importance of lilac flower oil in perfume industry, it was of interest to provide a new synthetic route for the alcohol (I). This has been achieved unambiguously but the route followed permits no steric control and as such (Scheme I) led to a mixture of all the possible (\pm)-diastereoisomers.

4,4-Ethylenedioxy-pentanal (III)³ was submitted to modified Wittig⁴ reaction with ethyl α -diethyl-phosphonopropionate in the presence of sodium hydride when ethyl 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-*trans*-hept-2-enoate (IV) was obtained in 75% yield. In view of the fact that the reaction of phosphonate carbanion with aldehydes tends to be stereospecific providing only *trans* isomers^{5,6}, the compound (IV) is given the

the keto-ester (V) yielded the tertiary alcohol (VI) in 68% yield, which upon reaction with sodium hydride⁷ in benzene furnished ethyl 2,6-dimethyl-3,6-epoxyoct-7-enoate (VII). Finally, the epoxy-ester (VII) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride provided the alcohol (I) on 62% yield.

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer, Infracord spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film and the NMR spectra were obtained in a 60 MHz instrument in carbon tetrachloride using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. The microanalyses were by L. K. Khullar.

Ethyl 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-trans-hept-2-enoate (IV): Sodium hydride (3.7 g) was placed in 1,2-dimethoxy ethane (150 ml). Ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate (18.3 g) was added dropwise below 20°C with stirring and the solution stirred until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resulting yellow solution was then added aldehyde (II; 10 g) slowly below 25°C and the solution was further stirred for 3 hr and then refluxed for 30 min. at 60°C. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with a large excess of water, dried (anh. Na₂SO₄) and evaporated. Distillation of the residue under reduced pressure provided α, β -unsaturated ester (IV; 12 g) in 75%, b.p. 135°C/3 mm., $\eta_D^{25} = 1.4870$ (Found: C, 62.76; H, 8.45; calc. for C₁₅H₂₀O₄: C, 63.13; H, 8.83%). γ_{max} 1720 cm⁻¹ (conjugated ester), 1650, 860 cm⁻¹ (tri-substituted double bond) and 1060 cm⁻¹ (ketal).

Ethyl 2-methyl-6-oxohept-2-enoate (V): The ketal (IV; 8 g) was dissolved in acetone (100 ml) and mixed with aq. hydrochloric acid (10%; 25 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temp. for 2 hr. The solution was diluted with brine solution and the product isolated by ether extraction. The ether layer was dried (anh. Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent and distillation under vacuum afforded the ketone (V, 4.5 g) in 69% yield; b.p. 115°C/3 mm., $\eta_D^{25} = 1.4810$ (Found: C, 64.75; H, 8.36; calc. for C₁₀H₁₆O₃: C, 65.19; H, 8.75%). γ_{max} 1720 cm⁻¹

trans configuration at the unsaturated linkage by analogy. The compound (IV) on deketalisation with dilute hydrochloric acid and acetone afforded in 69% yield of ethyl-2-methyl-6-oxohept-2-enoate (V), which was characterised through its IR spectrum, 2,4-DNPH and semicarbazone derivatives⁷. Inverse Grignard reaction with vinylmagnesiumbromide on

(br. > C = O), 1650, 860 cm^{-1} (tri-substituted double bond). Lit.⁶ reports IR peaks at 1721, 1713 and 1650 cm^{-1} .

The ketone (V) formed a 2,4-DNPH in yellow needles; m.p. 120–121°C after recrystallisation from ethanol (Found : N, 14.97. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 15.35%) and the semi-carbazone, m.p. 150–51°C on recrystallisation from dil. ethanol. (Found : N, 17.01; calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$: N, 17.42%. (Lit.⁶ m.p. 150.5–151.5°C).

2,6-Dimethyl-oct,2,7-dien-7-olate (VI) : Vinyl magnesium bromide, prepared from magnesium (1 g), vinyl bromide (6 g) in dry THF (60 ml), was added dropwise to a cooled and stirred solution of the keto-ester (V; 7 g) in dry THF (200 ml). The stirring was further continued for 2 hr and left overnight. The contents were refluxed for 1 hr and decomposed with ammonium chloride solution and the organic layer separated. The aqueous phase was extracted with ether and the combined organic extract was dried (anh. Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated. Distillation of the residue afforded 2,6-dimethyl-oct,2,7-dien-7-olate (VI; 5.5 g) in 68%; b.p. 130–33°C/3 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4550. (Found : C, 67.65; H, 8.86; calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 67.92; H, 9.44%). ν_{max} 3450, 1150 cm^{-1} (–OH), 1715 cm^{-1} (> C = O) 850 cm^{-1} (tri-substituted double bond) and 1650, 915 cm^{-1} (RHC = CH₂).

Ethyl 2,6-dimethyl-3,6-epoxy oct-7-enoate (VII) : The compound (VI; 5.5 g) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added slowly under nitrogen to a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (1.32 g) in dry benzene (75 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr. After cooling the excess of sodium hydride decomposed with ethanol, the residue obtained by the usual work up was chromatographed on silica gel (200 g). Elution with pet. ether : ether (95 : 5) provided the ether (VII) as a pale yellow oil. Distillation, which was accompanied by some decomposition, gave the pure product, b.p.

85–90°C/4 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4610 (Found : C, 67.53; H, 9.25; calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 67.92; H, 9.44%). ν_{max} 1735, 1650, 1190, 1180, 1040, 915 cm^{-1} . Lit.⁶ records peaks at 1735, 1184, 1048 cm^{-1} .

2,6-Dimethyl-3,6-epoxyoct-7-enol (I) : To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.1 g.) in dry ether (60 ml) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of the ester (VII; 1 g) in ether (15 ml) so as to keep the ether at a gentle reflux. The contents were further stirred for 3 hr at room temp. and the metal-complex was decomposed with sodium potassium tartrate solution (20%). Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded the alcohol (I; 0.6 g) in 62% yield, b.p. 98–100°C/7–8 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4660. (Found : C, 70.46; H, 10.28; calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$: C, 70.59; H, 10.59%). ν_{max} 3520, 1050 cm^{-1} (–OH), 3105, 1640, 990, 920 cm^{-1} (–CH = CH₂) and 1020 cm^{-1} (–O–) comparable to those reported in literature¹.

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